

The Transmedia Publicity of Swiss Banks: Public Relations Strategies and Mass Media Coverage (1960–1977)

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Although many stories keep with Swiss banking, the historical determinants and modalities of information publicly available on Swiss banks have remained out of historiography's interest.¹ This paper examines how transmedia might be used as a method to inquire into the publicity of Swiss banks. In the 1960s and 1970s, Swiss banks became increasingly present on the radio and the television (TV). This added to a long-standing press coverage and herewith amplified and diversified their publicity. Information, images and ideas about Swiss banks circulated across several media simultaneously. Meanwhile, modern public relations (PR) techniques were explored in Swiss industries, including banking. While Swiss banks had long kept 'low-key', they began experimenting with broader PR campaigns. With that in mind, how was public information about banks shaped in the 1960s and 1970s? To answer this question, this paper addresses the rise of Swiss banks' 'transmedia publicity' in the 1960s and up until the Chiasso scandal of 1977, through the PR strategies of the Swiss Bankers' Association (SBA) and the mass-media coverage of banking in Switzerland. It uses the SBA's physical archives, its digitised archives, SBA publicist Leo Schürmann's archives, as well as digitised mass-media archives, for which it draws from the databases of *Radio Television Suisse* (RTS), *Schweizer Radio und Fernsehen* (SRF), *Impresso*² and *e-newspaperarchives*.³ Scientific literature on this topic is virtually non-existent, except for two exploratory works that benefitted from limited first-hand and mass-media archives (Guex and Mazbouri 2013; Agthe 2016).

Throughout the twentieth century, the Swiss banking sector was characterised by extended joint communication. The industry's business association, the SBA, played a central role in publicising banks, their image and values (Guex and Mazbouri 2013). It engaged in what it called indistinctly "Propaganda", "Public Relations", "Öffentlichkeitsarbeit", and "Publizität", to arguably "make the public aware of the important role played by banks in the country's economic life and the advantages that their services can offer everyone".⁴ In fact, it promoted pro-bank and pro-business messages through media financing and content creation (Agthe 2016). Although banks preferred discretion over mass media exposure (Guex and Haver 2007), the association established a commission for permanent publicity efforts in 1948, the *Kommission für Publizitätsfragen* (KfP).⁵ Members were responsible for linking with newspapers in their areas.⁶ The KfP sent them instructions, while also

¹ This paper presents early results of an ongoing doctoral research carried out as part of the project "Impresso - Media Monitoring of the Past II. Beyond Borders: Connecting Historical Newspapers and Radio" (<https://impresso-project.ch/project/>), jointly funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF 213585) and the Luxembourg National Research Fund (17498891). The thesis' working title is "Swiss Banks on Display. A History of the Publicity of Swiss Banks in the 20th Century Through the Public Relations of the Swiss Bankers' Association and Mass-Media Coverage (1913-1991)". It is supervised by Raphaëlle Ruppen Coutaz (University of Lausanne).

² <https://impresso-project.ch/app/>

³ <https://www.e-newspaperarchives.ch/>

⁴ Schweizerische Wirtschaftsarchiv (SWA) (Basel), PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from the secretariat (Oetterli) to Philippe de Thibault de Boesinghe, 'Publicité bancaire', 12 March 1964, p. 1; all quotes in German and in French are translated by the author.

⁵ Swiss Bankers Association's Archives (SBAA), VR184Prot_VGgescannt, 'Vorbericht zur 184. Sitzung des Verwaltungsrates der Schweizerischen Bankiervereinigung', 22 September 1947, p. 6.

⁶ SBAA, VRA101Prot_VGgescannt, 'Protokoll der 101. Sitzung des Ausschusses der Schweizerischen Bankiervereinigung', 25 February 1948, p. 10-11.

relying on their own initiatives.⁷ They maintained ties with editorial staffs, especially liberal-conservative press, which collaborated willingly and shared bankers' views.⁸ They published articles and were active in the local public sphere. Besides, the KfP, whose PR exceeded banking topics, operated within the "complex nebula" of corporate influence (Longchamp 2014, 247), aligning with anti-tax, anti-statist, and anti-socialist groups financed by big business since the 1930s (Eichenberger and Leimgruber 2024).

In the 1960s-1970s, the KfP started engaging with radio and television, viewed as means to reach "outsiders".⁹ It encouraged bankers to participate to economic chronicles and information programmes,¹⁰ while occasionally coordinating such efforts,¹¹ like on *Erwachsenen-Bildung* in 1965.¹² The SBA insisted on selecting interviewers and questions.¹³ Partners included NBC, BBC, and *Süddeutschen Rundfunk*, but it also produced a series for SRG's English-speaking international broadcasting titled, "Swiss Banks: Myths and Reality".¹⁴ Furthermore, following liberalisation of advertising on public broadcast in 1965 (Rostan 2017), banks chose joint advertising led by the KfP over individual advertising.¹⁵

Meanwhile, the KfP bolstered its presence in the press beyond liberal-conservative outlets, most notably to local newspapers, and youth and women's magazines. It also partnered with journals such as *Switzerland Today* and *Wirtschaft und Recht* on special issues comprising bankers' articles. Some were mailed to Switzerland diplomatic representations for dispatch overseas, as exemplified by a 1967 article in Manila's *Sunday Times Variety* titled "The Truth About Swiss Banking".¹⁶ Initially hesitant about foreign media, the KfP selectively engaged with foreign press, publishing in outlets like *The Times* (UK), *Correio da Manhã* (Brazil), *Valeurs Actuelles* (France), *Southern Economist* (India) and *Svenska Dagbladet* (Sweden). Efforts remained limited and deliberate, avoiding mass coverage. In this regard, the SBA repeatedly rebuffed PR companies' offers. Be it in Switzerland or abroad, the KfP intervened when an article wasn't going banks' way.¹⁷

The KfP's content was remarkably homogeneous. It usually consisted of pro-bank messages draped in educative or technical narratives, as instanced by 1963 articles "L'argent et les banques" and "Que se passe-t-il à la Bourse?",¹⁸ or by the specialist press article "The Evolution of Swiss Banks".¹⁹ If no transmedia campaign was launched as such, the SBA sought a strategic presence in the media ecosystem. Material was framed according to a common standard, contributing to a coherent coverage. The SBA's PR can therefore be understood as an instance of "organised persuasive communication" (Bakir et al. 2019) or "practices of influence" (Cohen 2017). They used a kind of "transmedia advertising" (Mendiz and García Avis 2017), i.e. transmedia PR strategies.

⁷ Ibid., p. 11

⁸ See for example: SWA PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from Michel Petitpierre (Journal de Genève) to A. Herminjard (Banque cantonale vaudoise), 13 February 1968; Swiss Federal Archives (SFA) (Bern), Nachlass (NL) Leo Schürmann, SFA J1.298#2003/36#2182*, letter from L. Schürmann to C. Mötteli (NZZ), 4 March 1958; SFA, NL Leo Schürmann, J1.298#2003/36#2174*, letter from D. Barth (Basler Nachrichten) to L. Schürmann, 30 June 1951.

⁹ SFA, NL Leo Schürmann, J1.298#2003/36#4023*, letter from Leo Schürmann to E. Roesle, 3 July 1951, p. 2.

¹⁰ Quoted in: SWA PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from the secretariat to KfP members, 15 November 1962, p. 5. To the best of my knowledge, no agenda or minutes of this meeting were preserved.

¹¹ SFA, NL Leo Schürmann, J1.298#2003/36#411*, 'Protokoll der Sitzung der Kommission für Publizitätsfragen', 22 November 1962, p. 12.

¹² SWA PA 650, G-3-0-1160, 'Protokoll der Sitzung des Arbeitsausschusses der Publizitätskommission', 26 February 1965, p. 4.

¹³ SWA PA 650, G-3-0-1160, letter from Schweizerische Volksbank (V. Krügler) to the KfP president (H. Bauer), 'Publizität der Banken am Radio "Die Börse ist nicht nur zum Spekulieren da"', 20 January 1967; SWA PA 650, G-3-0-1160, 'Protokoll der Sitzung des Arbeitsausschusses der Publizitätskommission', 26 February 1965, p. 2.

¹⁴ SWA PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from the SBA (Oetterli) to Joël Curchod (SRG), 10 February 1967.

¹⁵ SWA PA 650, G-3-0-1160, letter from the secretariat to KfP members, 18 October 1965, p. 1.

¹⁶ SWA PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from the Federal Political Department to the SBA, 14 September 1967.

¹⁷ See for example: SFA, NL Leo Schürmann, J1.298#2003/36#2174*, letter from L. Schürmann to R. Deonna (carbon copy), 13 August 1951.

¹⁸ SWA PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from Wirtschaftsförderung (L. Simeon) to the SBA, 'unsere Bildreportage: "Das Geld und die Banken" und "Was geht an der Börse vor?"', 17 August 1964.

¹⁹ SWA PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from Oetterli (SBA) to Statist, 11 July 1966.

Figure 8: 'Bank' Mentions in French-speaking and German-speaking Newspapers in Switzerland (1913–91).²⁰

Figure 9: Frequency of 'Bank' in French-speaking Newspapers in Switzerland (1913–91). See Figure 1 for Impreso collection breakdown. Sources: <https://impresso-project.ch/app/>, consulted on 13 January 2025.

Were transmedia PR strategies correlated with transmedia publicity? In other words, did they succeed? From press perspective, figures 1 and 2 reveal that newspapers reported significantly and increasingly more on banks in the second half of the twentieth century. The coverage steadily increased between the 1950s–1990s, rising nearly fourfold and reflecting the economic growth of Swiss banks during this period (Mazbouri, Guex, and Lopez 2021; Michelet 2023). Peaks often

²⁰ The Impreso collection (orange) comprises all French-speaking newspapers in the Impreso database which are entirely available over the period 1913–91: Journal de Genève, Gazette de Lausanne, L'Express, La Liberté, L'Impartial, Le Confédéré. The e-newspaperarchives.ch collection (red) comprises all German-speaking newspapers in the e-newspaperarchives.ch database which are entirely available over the period 1913–91: der Bund, Berner Tagwacht, Bieler Tagblatt, Bote vom Untersee und Rhein, Burgdorfer Tagblatt, Engadiner Post, Freiburger Nachrichten, die Gewerkschaft, Neue Zürcher Nachrichten, Neue Zürcher Zeitung, Nidwaldner Volksblatt, SMUV-Zeitung, der Schweizer Arbeitnehmer, VHTL-Zeitung, Walliser Bote. Sources: <https://impresso-project.ch/app/> and <https://www.e-newspaperarchives.ch/>, consulted on 13 January 2025.

coincided with crises, such as in 1914, 1931, 1978, and the late 1980s, periods marked by bank failures or takeovers (Giddey and Mazbouri 2022, 256). The period 1955–85 established banking as a focus for newspapers, significantly boosting the publicity of Swiss banks with both positive and negative narratives. Regarding public broadcast, information expanded on both radio and television in the 1960s–1970s (Vallotton 2006), sparking debates about the politicisation of SRG on economic issues (Schneider 2006). Quantitative analysis of bank coverage remains difficult due to fragmented archives. Preserved sources featuring banks include newsflash, documentaries, interviews, debates, and one fiction. A key characteristic was the presence of experts. KfP members and major banks' CEOs participated in information programmes, discussing matters pertaining the economy or the industry in general, rather than their banks.

A striking example was Philippe de Weck, *Union Bank of Switzerland* CEO, who made 27 appearances between 1967 and 1979. He featured on six TV programmes and five radio shows, including six times on *Un jour une heure*. In *En direct avec...* (18 June 1975, one hour), he discussed banking secrecy, banks' financial might, and the Swiss franc. In *En question* (2 November 1976, one hour), he covered his career, banking laws, and Swiss banks' activities. Additionally, he joined a debate on banking regulation during *Table ouverte* (TV, 1977), following the Chiasso money laundering scandal. De Weck's presence contrasted with that of banks' critics: between those two interviews, Swiss-French radio cancelled an interview of socialist MP Jean Ziegler about a book of his, which critically assessed the activity of Swiss banks (Vallotton 2006, 71). De Weck, on the other hand, regularly gave in-depth interviews lasting twenty-plus minutes, ranging from European financial markets, Swiss monetary policies, and the 1970s economic crisis to Swiss democracy, Geneva's international relations school (HEI), and the *Neue Zürcher Zeitung*. He never directly discussed his bank, positioning himself as the go-to banking expert. There is no record of such extended media presence for any banker. De Weck, it appears, was one of the first of his kind to gain a media stature. In 1970, he received the second ever "prize of contact" awarded by Swiss-French economic journalists for his good relations with the press.²¹ Philippe de Weck fostered the transmedia publicity of Swiss banks as he propagated banks' views across several media simultaneously. His case not only shows that the SBA's PR succeeded to a certain extent but also that access to information on banks depended on bankers themselves, at least partly.

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